

Chromium (III)-phosphoric Acid Complex

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The stability constant of the complex, CrHPO_4^+ , has been determined electrometrically as well as spectrophotometrically. The former method provides a value 2.82×10^9 and latter, 2.56×10^9 . Very little dependence of the stability constant on temperature indicates the ΔH of formation to be nearly zero.

Jameson and Salmon¹ found no complex formation at 0° between Cr (III) ion and phosphoric acid; but at 40° they observed in ion-exchange studies both cationic and anionic complexes, viz., $[\text{Cr}(\text{HPO}_4)_2]^+$ and, less probably, $[\text{CrH}_2\text{PO}_4]^{2+}$ and $[\text{Cr}(\text{PO}_4)_3]^{3-}$. Holroyd and Salmon² showed that complex formation could be represented by the equation:

the reaction being a slow one. Though equilibrium was reached in about three weeks at 40°, it probably did not attain equilibrium at 25° even after nine weeks. In the present communication, the evaluation of the stability constant of chromium-phosphate complex has been attempted.

EXPERIMENTAL

Chromic perchlorate was prepared in two different ways. Firstly, starting with chromic oxide (CrO_3) (G.R.-E.M.) and perchloric acid (G.R.-E.M.), chromic perchlorate was prepared by reducing the resulting solution with hydrogen peroxide (30% G.R.-E.M.) and subsequently decomposing the excess peroxide. Secondly, from a solution of chromic sulphate (Baker, Analysed). Chromic hydroxide, $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3$, was precipitated with ammonium hydroxide. The precipitate was washed free of sulphates and then dissolved in excess perchloric acid solution. The chromium content in the solution was estimated iodometrically as well as by using standard Mohr's salt (G.R.-E.M.) solution. The free acid content in the solutions was also estimated. All other chemicals used were of reagent grade. The solutions were prepared in double-distilled water.

All optical density measurements were taken with a Beckman DU Spectrophotometer. For the pH measurements a Cambridge Bench type, battery-operated pH-meter was used. To ensure attainment of the equilibrium, all the solutions were aged for more than two months at 40° and then kept at the temperature of measurement for about two weeks before measurements were taken.

1. *J. Chem. Soc.* 1955, 340.

2. *Ibid.*, 1956, 289.

Composition of the Complex

As the reaction between the chromium ion and phosphoric acid is known to be slow, several solutions containing chromium perchlorate and phosphoric acid at different initial pHs but

at a constant ionic strength of 0.25 M were placed in a thermostat at 40°. The change in optical density of the solutions were followed from day to day. In Fig. 1 optical density has been plotted against number of hours. The optical density increases at a constant rate in the beginning and the rate falls to reach a constant value, indicating attainment of equilibrium.

FIG. 1

would lead one to mean that CrHPO_4^+ is formed, or may be that both CrHPO_4^+ and $\text{CrH}_2\text{PO}_4^{2+}$ are present. On the basis of the fact that under similar experimental conditions in the case of ferric-phosphoric acid complex, only FeHPO_4^+ is formed and also that Holroyd and Salmon⁸ report the evidence of mainly CrHPO_4^+ , we assume that the complex is mainly CrHPO_4^+ . The constancy of the equilibrium constant, calculated on the basis of the presence of this complex (*vide infra*), justifies our assumption.

Calculation of the Equilibrium Constant from pH Measurements

The chromium-phosphate complex at equilibrium in solution may be represented as

the equilibrium constant

$$K = \frac{a_{\text{CrHPO}_4^+}}{a_{\text{Cr}^{3+}} \times a_{\text{HPO}_4^{2-}}} = \frac{C_{\text{CrHPO}_4^+}}{C_{\text{Cr}^{3+}} \times C_{\text{HPO}_4^{2-}}} \times \frac{f_+}{f_3 \times f_2}$$

The concentrations of the different species in the equation have been calculated from the pH of the chromic perchlorate solution equilibrated with phosphoric acid in the following way.

The pH_s , the solution would have had there been no reaction, could be experimentally determined by adding known amounts of phosphoric acid to a solution containing perchloric acid to have the pH of the chromic perchlorate solution. This pH , i.e., the pH the solution would attain on addition of a known amount of phosphoric acid, could as well be calculated by taking into account the change in the dissociation of phosphoric acid by successive approximations. Both the calculated and the experimentally determined values agreed.

In our work, the pH_s , the solutions would have on addition of a known amount of phosphoric acid had there been no reaction, were calculated by the method of approximation. In a number of cases, the pH_s were checked by actual measurements of pH_s of solutions of only perchloric acid (having the pH of the aged chromic perchlorate solution) with known amounts of phosphoric acid.

From the difference in the pH_s of the solution, where reaction has resulted and what it would have been had there been no reaction, the $CrHPO_4^+$ has been calculated in the same way as described earlier³⁻⁵. The concentrations of Cr^{3+} ions and also $\alpha_{H_2PO_4^-}$ have been obtained in the same manner as described earlier³⁻⁵. For the activity coefficients, the Davies empirical equation⁵ has been used. The results are shown in Table I.

TABLE I
Temp. = 25°.

Concentration of $Cr(ClO_4)_3$ ($M \times 10^3$).	H_2PO_4 ($M \times 10^3$).	pH of the		μ .	$C_{(CrHPO_4^+)}$ ($M \times 10^3$).	$K \times 10^9$.
		Mixture.	Blank (calc.)			
10.0	10.0	1.81	2.09	0.10	5.98	2.23
10.0	20.0	1.66	1.91	0.10	7.39	2.38
20.0	20.0	1.53	1.79	0.20	10.45	3.06
20.0	30.0	1.48	1.71	0.20	10.51	1.86
30.0	30.0	1.38	1.65	0.30	15.09	4.48
30.0	60.0	1.30	1.55	0.30	16.80	2.73
40.0	40.0	1.30	1.56	0.40	17.72	3.73
40.0	60.0	1.22	1.50	0.40	22.10	4.76
18.7	60.0	1.42	1.60	0.18	9.60	1.39
13.3	40.0	1.50	1.70	0.15	8.74	1.59

Average $K = 2.82 \times 10^9$

The average value of the stability constant for the complex $CrHPO_4^+$ comes out to be 2.82×10^9 at 25°.

Equilibrium Constant by Spectrophotometric Method

The overall equilibrium between chromic ion and phosphoric acid may be written as

3. Lahiry and Aditya, *this Journal*, 1964, 41, 517.

4. Lahiri, *ibid.*, 1965, 42, 715.

5. *J. Chem. Soc.* 1939, 2093.

If C_1 and C_2 be the concentrations of chromic perchlorate and phosphoric acid, respectively, and X , the concentration of CrHPO_4^+ , the equilibrium constant K' can be represented as

$$K' = \frac{a_{\text{CrHPO}_4^+} \times a_{\text{H}^+}^3}{a_{\text{Cr}^{3+}} \times a_{\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4}}$$

At constant pH

$$\begin{aligned} K'' &= \frac{K'}{a_{\text{H}^+}^3} = \frac{C_{\text{CrHPO}_4^+}}{C_{\text{Cr}^{3+}} \times C_{\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4}} \times \frac{f_+}{f_{3+}} \\ &= \frac{X}{(C_1 - X)(C_2 - X)} \times \frac{f_+}{f_{3+}} \end{aligned}$$

At constant ionic strength, (f_+/f_{3+}) can be regarded as fixed. This equation, thus reduces on rearrangement to

$$\frac{C_1}{d_2 - d_1} = \frac{1}{(\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1)l} + \frac{1}{(\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1)l(C_2 - X)} \cdot \frac{1}{K''}$$

where d_1 and d_2 are the optical densities of a solution of chromic perchlorate and a solution containing a mixture of chromic perchlorate and phosphoric acid, respectively; ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 are the molar extinction coefficients of chromic perchlorate and chromic phosphate in solution, respectively, and l , the optical length of the cell.

As already mentioned, the equilibrium takes a long time and as such pH adjustment before the optical density measurement is not possible. Because of this, it was difficult to obtain $1/(\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1)$ and $1/K''$ by approximation method from measurements with solutions containing only chromic perchlorate and phosphoric acid. So for the determination of $1/(\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1)$, which can be assumed to be roughly taken to be independent of ionic strength, we have used a buffer solution containing NaH_2PO_4 and H_2PO_4 for reaction with chromic perchlorate such that the pH and the ionic strength (although high) are practically fixed, and measured the optical densities of these solutions. For obtaining the optical densities of chromic perchlorate (aged) at that pH, chromic perchlorate was allowed to age at different pHs. Using the curve for extinction coefficient against pH, the d_1 's were calculated. Then following the method of approximation in graphical plots, as was done in our earlier work^{3,4}, $1/(\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1)$ has been obtained.

Once $1/(\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1)$ has been obtained, the concentration of CrHPO_4^+ species in any solution can be easily calculated, followed by calculation of the stability constant of the species CrHPO_4^+ .

For calculation of the thermodynamic stability constant, we have taken solutions containing only chromic perchlorate and phosphoric acid. The results are shown in Table II.

The average value of K_{stab} is 2.56×10^6 corresponding to ΔF° of -12.83 kcal at 25° .

The optical densities of a number of the equilibrated solutions at 25°, 35°, and 45° were measured, but no appreciable change in optical density was observed. This indicates that the heat of formation ($-\Delta H$) is zero or if at all, it must be small. Taking $\Delta H=0$, ΔS comes out to be ≈ 4.3 e.u.

TABLE II

Temp. = 25°.

 $1/(\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1) = 0.038$ (determined) at 260 m μ .

Concentration of		d_2	d_1	Conc. of	pH.	μ	$K \times 10^{-9}$
Cr(ClO ₄) ₃ ($M \times 10^3$) (C_1).	H ₃ PO ₄ ($M \times 10^3$) (C_2).			CrHPO ₄ ⁺ ($M \times 10^3$)			
20.0	20.0	0.550	0.282	10.18	1.53	0.2	2.94
20.0	30.0	0.590	0.278	11.86	1.48	0.2	2.51
30.0	30.0	0.741	0.480	12.66	1.38	0.3	2.77
30.0	60.0	0.777	0.309	14.36	1.30	0.3	1.85
40.0	40.0	0.940	0.532	15.51	1.30	0.4	2.66
40.0	60.0	0.962	0.532	16.34	1.22	0.4	2.31
50.0	50.0	1.102	0.665	16.61	1.17	0.5	2.87

Av. $K=2.56 \times 10^9$

DISCUSSIONS

Since HPO₄²⁻ may be regarded as a bidentate group, the formation of a four-membered ring may be possible with Cr³⁺ ion as in the case of Fe²⁺ and Fe³⁺ ions^{2,4} for which the optimum radius of metal ion is 0.7 Å. The ionic radii of Fe²⁺ and Cr³⁺ ions are 0.64 and ≈ 0.7 Å⁷, respectively. As such we would expect chromic complex to be more stable because chelation with Fe²⁺ ion will involve more strain, whereas that with Cr³⁺ will have very little strain. But the experimental values for the phosphate complexes show just the reverse order. This is of course in agreement with the general observations.

The stability of the chromic complex must be due to entropy effect as there is decrease in charge due to complex formation.

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6. Genge and Salmon, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 1459.

7. Pauling, "The Nature of the Chemical Bond". Cornell University Press, Ithaca, N.Y., 3rd ed., p. 216.